

Striped Magic Squares of Order 18

Inder J. Taneja¹

The whole work as pdf file is available at author's site:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=11911>

Abstract

*This work brings magic squares of order 18 based on **equal width magic rectangles**. These are magic rectangles of type 2×4 , 2×6 , 2×8 , etc. Alternatively, we can write it as $2 \times n$, where n is the length of magic rectangle. Magic squares constructed based on **equal width magic rectangles**, we call as **striped magic squares**. For the **striped** magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14 and 16 refer the author's work [94, 95]. The whole work is with 4363 **striped magic squares** is available as **pdf file** at author's web-site. The link is as given above.*

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Contents

1 Introduction	3
1.1 Bordered Double Digits Magic Rectangles	3
1.2 Striped Cornered Magic Rectangles	4
1.3 Stripes of Equal Width	6
2 Striped Magic Squares of Order 18	6
2.1 Part 1: Embedded with Striped Magic Squares of Order 14	7
2.2 Part 2: Embedded with Symmetric Magic Rectangles	10
2.3 Part 3: Cornered with Striped Magic Squares of Order 14	11
2.4 Part 4: Cornered with Striped Magic Squares of Order 12: Using Algebraic Formula $(a + b)^2 = a^2 + b^2 + 2ab$	13
2.5 Part 5: Cornered with Striped Magic Squares of Order 12	15
2.6 Part 6: Cornered with Striped Magic Squares of Order 10 Using Algebraic Formula $(a + b)^2 = a^2 + b^2 + 2ab$	17
2.7 Part 7: Embedded with Striped Magic Squares of Order 14	19
2.8 Part 8: Some Extra Magic Squares of Order 18	21
2.9 Part 9: Cornered with Striped Magic Squares of Order 16	23
3 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers	25

1 Introduction

Let's understand first about **striped magic rectangles**, i.e., **equal width magic rectangles**. These are of orders 2×4 , 2×4 , 2×4 , etc. It is based on following two ideas recently, developed by the author:

- (i) Striped Bordered Double Digits Magic Rectangles.
- (ii) Striped Cornered Magic Rectangles.

The above two items are not known in the literature of magic squares. Let's understand one by one.

1.1 Bordered Double Digits Magic Rectangles

Here we shall bring double digits bordered magic rectangles. See below few examples.

Example 1.1. Below is an example of **double digit bordered magic rectangle** of order 6×14 :

11	8	7	71	5	70	69	73	84	23	26	63	13	72	595
74	77	78	14	80	15	16	12	1	62	59	22	76	9	595
66	19	52	42	50	40	41	47	34	37	36	46	24	61	595
65	20	33	43	35	45	44	38	51	48	49	39	57	28	595
10	75	81	27	68	67	21	53	30	3	25	2	79	54	595
29	56	4	58	17	18	64	32	55	82	60	83	6	31	595
255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255

The magic rectangle of width 2 are of equal sums. See below:

11	8	7	71	5	70	69	73	84	23	26	63	510
74	77	78	14	80	15	16	12	1	62	59	22	510
85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	
81	27	68	67	21	53	30	3	25	2	79	54	510
4	58	17	18	64	32	55	82	60	83	6	31	510
85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	
			13	72	85		66	19	85			
			76	9	85		65	20	85			
			24	61	85		10	75	85			
			57	28	85		29	56	85			
			170	170			170	170				

Example 1.2. Below is an another example of **double digit bordered magic rectangle** of order 10×12 :

108	4	10	106	19	96	100	103	36	23	109	12	726
13	117	111	15	102	25	21	18	85	98	116	5	726
20	101	43	81	70	42	82	45	50	71	120	1	726
91	30	78	40	51	79	39	76	37	84	31	90	726
89	32	54	67	57	60	63	62	75	46	9	112	726
104	17	55	66	64	61	58	59	80	41	86	35	726
34	87	65	56	83	48	72	47	44	69	11	110	726
114	7	68	53	38	73	49	74	77	52	2	119	726
3	118	6	14	93	22	97	95	27	113	105	33	726
29	92	115	107	28	99	24	26	94	8	16	88	726
605	605	605	605	605	605	605	605	605	605	605	605	

The magic rectangle of width 2 are of equal sums. See below:

108	4	10	106	19	96	100	103	36	23	605	20	101	121	109	12	121	43	81	70	42	82	45	363	54	67	121	50	71	121						
13	117	111	15	102	25	21	18	85	98	605	91	30	121	116	5	121	78	40	51	79	39	76	363	55	66	121	37	84	121						
121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	89	32	121	120	1	121	121	121	121	121	121	121		65	56	121	75	46	121						
											104	17	121	31	90	121								68	53	121	80	41	121						
											34	87	121	9	112	121								242	242		242	242							
											114	7	121	86	35	121	83	48	72	47	44	69	363												
											3	118	121	11	110	121	38	73	49	74	77	52	363							57	60	63	62	242	
											29	92	121	2	119	121	121	121	121	121	121	121		64	61	58	59	242							
											484	484		484	484									121	121	121	121								

We observe that in all the above examples, the width of magic rectangles is always 2. The differences are only in the length.

1.2 Striped Cornered Magic Rectangles

We observe from **double digits magic rectangles** that magic rectangles are with width 2, i.e., these are of magic rectangles of type 2×4 , 2×6 , 2×8 , etc. But this property is not true for the cornered magic rectangles [83]. Below are few examples where we have **cornered magic rectangles** with the property every magic rectangle is with width 2.

Example 1.3. Below is an example of a **striped cornered magic rectangle** of order 6×14 :

52	47	40	37	42	36	41	50	34	46	58	27	12	73	595
33	38	45	48	43	49	44	35	51	39	60	25	74	11	595
26	66	32	64	65	31	22	28	61	30	29	56	4	81	595
59	19	53	21	20	54	63	57	24	55	23	62	78	7	595
71	69	72	5	6	67	70	3	68	2	1	76	77	8	595
14	16	13	80	79	18	15	82	17	83	84	9	10	75	595
255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255

The sums are as follows:

71 69 72 5 6 67 70 3 68 2 1 76	510	12 73	85	58 27	85
14 16 13 80 79 18 15 82 17 83 84 9	510	74 11	85	60 25	85
85 85 85 85 85 85 85 85 85 85 85 85		4 81	85	29 56	85
		78 7	85	23 62	85
26 66 32 64 65 31 22 28 61 30	425	77 8	85	170 170	
59 19 53 21 20 54 63 57 24 55	425	10 75	85		
85 85 85 85 85 85 85 85 85 85		255 255			
52 47 40 37 42 36 41 50 34 46	425				
33 38 45 48 43 49 44 35 51 39	425				
85 85 85 85 85 85 85 85 85 85					

Example 1.4. Below is an example of another **striped cornered magic rectangle** of order 10×12 :

59 61 64 58	68 53	73 48	86 35	18 103	726
62 60 57 63	50 71	76 45	24 97	108 13	726
72 65 54 51	69 52	46 75	22 99	8 113	726
49 56 67 70	55 66	41 80	98 23	104 17	726
74 84 81 39	42 43	44 77	29 92	102 19	726
47 37 40 82	79 78	83 38	34 87	15 106	726
90 26 33 96	94 32	85 28	91 30	115 6	726
31 95 88 25	27 89	36 93	100 21	114 7	726
109 116 2 118	1 4	112 16	107 20	11 110	726
12 5 119 3	120 117	9 105	14 101	10 111	726
605 605 605 605	605 605	605 605	605 605	605 605	

The sums are as follows:

109 116 2 118 1 4 112 16 107 20	605	18 103	121	86 35	121	73 48	121	68 53	121
12 5 119 3 120 117 9 105 14 101	605	108 13	121	24 97	121	76 45	121	50 71	121
121 121 121 121 121 121 121 121 121 121		8 113	121	22 99	121	46 75	121	69 52	121
		104 17	121	98 23	121	41 80	121	55 66	121
90 26 33 96 94 32 85 28	484	102 19	121	29 92	121	44 77	121	242 242	
31 95 88 25 27 89 36 93	484	15 106	121	34 87	121	83 38	121		
121 121 121 121 121 121 121 121		115 6	121	91 30	121	363 363			
		114 7	121	100 21	121				
74 84 81 39 42 43	363	11 110	121	484 484					
47 37 40 82 79 78	363	10 111	121						
121 121 121 121 121 121		605 605							
72 65 54 51	242	59 61 64 58	242						
49 56 67 70	242	62 60 57 63	242						
121 121 121 121		121 121 121 121							

1.3 Stripes of Equal Width

Whole the work is based on equal width magic rectangles of order $2 \times n$, where $n = 4, 6, \dots 18$. These are as follows:

From the above example, we observe that in the all the case, the width is always 325. The length changes according to the order of magic rectangle.

2 Striped Magic Squares of Order 18

In this work there are total 4363 **striped magic squares** of order 18. This we have divided in different parts as subsections. Still there are many squares as semi-magic squares. Later on these shall be transfered to magic squares by simple calculations.

2.1 Part 1: Embedded with Striped Magic Squares of Order 14

This part is with striped magic squares of order 18. In this part, we have embedded striped magic squares of order 14 studied before [94] . It already contains striped magic squares of orders 6 and 10. Below are few examples. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author’s site [96].

1	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925	
	1	3	323	321	320	6	318	8	9	315	11	313	312	14	310	16	17	308	2925
	324	322	2	4	5	319	7	317	316	10	314	12	13	311	15	309	19	306	2925
	49	276	65	67	259	257	256	255	71	72	73	251	75	249	77	248	307	18	2925
	275	50	260	258	66	68	69	70	254	253	252	74	250	76	79	246	305	20	2925
	51	274	101	224	115	113	211	209	208	118	206	120	121	204	247	78	304	21	2925
	273	52	223	102	210	212	114	116	117	207	119	205	123	202	245	80	22	303	2925
	272	53	103	222	137	188	155	172	154	169	147	178	203	122	244	81	302	23	2925
	54	271	221	104	187	138	170	153	171	156	180	145	201	124	243	82	24	301	2925
	270	55	220	105	139	186	150	173	176	151	146	179	200	125	83	242	25	300	2925
	56	269	219	106	185	140	175	152	149	174	177	148	126	199	84	241	299	26	2925
	57	268	107	218	184	141	165	157	164	163	159	167	198	127	85	240	27	298	2925
	267	58	108	217	182	143	160	168	161	162	166	158	128	197	239	86	297	28	2925
	59	266	109	216	144	181	129	195	131	193	136	134	190	192	87	238	296	29	2925
	265	60	111	214	142	183	196	130	194	132	189	191	135	133	237	88	30	295	2925
	264	61	215	110	89	235	91	233	232	231	95	96	97	99	227	225	294	31	2925
	262	63	213	112	236	90	234	92	93	94	230	229	228	226	98	100	32	293	2925
	64	261	33	291	35	289	288	38	286	40	41	283	43	281	280	278	48	46	2925
	62	263	292	34	290	36	37	287	39	285	284	42	282	44	45	47	277	279	2925
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

4	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925	
	324	322	12	271	314	279	62	5	301	63	7	39	16	270	311	272	49	8	2925
	1	3	313	54	11	46	263	320	24	262	318	286	309	55	14	53	276	317	2925
	52	273	257	109	248	218	92	90	230	67	81	242	254	88	213	86	302	23	2925
	303	22	68	216	77	107	233	235	95	258	244	83	71	237	112	239	265	60	2925
	58	267	72	253	208	133	184	125	132	130	186	203	205	119	260	65	36	289	2925
	13	312	219	106	117	192	141	200	193	195	139	122	120	206	74	251	27	298	2925
	284	41	225	100	197	128	155	170	150	175	147	178	194	131	226	99	32	293	2925
	278	47	78	247	116	209	172	153	173	152	180	145	113	212	101	224	25	300	2925
	15	310	234	91	142	183	154	171	176	149	146	179	137	188	89	236	61	264	2925
	304	21	103	222	118	207	169	156	151	174	177	148	204	121	220	105	261	64	2925
	40	285	85	240	191	134	165	157	164	163	159	167	140	185	238	87	283	42	2925
	19	306	252	73	211	114	160	168	161	162	166	158	187	138	82	243	288	37	2925
	319	6	246	79	115	201	129	136	190	199	182	144	127	202	108	217	321	4	2925
	274	51	111	214	210	124	196	189	135	126	143	181	198	123	227	98	287	38	2925
	299	26	96	223	221	66	70	110	250	231	93	76	241	256	97	245	31	294	2925
	17	308	229	102	104	259	255	215	75	94	232	249	84	69	228	80	56	269	2925
	266	307	45	57	275	29	315	20	35	277	291	323	9	292	282	44	28	30	2925
	59	18	280	268	50	296	10	305	290	48	34	2	316	33	43	281	297	295	2925
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

29	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925	
	324	322	12	271	314	279	62	5	301	63	7	39	16	270	311	272	49	8	2925
	1	3	313	54	11	46	263	320	24	262	318	286	309	55	14	53	276	317	2925
	52	273	257	109	248	218	92	90	230	67	81	242	254	88	213	86	302	23	2925
	303	22	68	216	77	107	233	235	95	258	244	83	71	237	112	239	265	60	2925
	58	267	72	253	113	212	123	202	129	196	137	188	145	180	260	65	36	289	2925
	13	312	219	106	115	210	203	122	193	132	185	140	179	146	74	251	27	298	2925
	284	41	225	100	211	114	121	204	136	189	182	143	147	178	226	99	32	293	2925
	278	47	78	247	209	116	128	197	192	133	187	138	177	148	101	224	25	300	2925
	15	310	234	91	208	117	200	125	190	135	144	181	176	149	89	236	61	264	2925
	304	21	103	222	206	119	126	199	134	191	142	183	150	175	220	105	261	64	2925
	40	285	85	240	118	207	198	127	195	130	139	186	174	151	238	87	283	42	2925
	19	306	252	73	120	205	201	124	131	194	184	141	152	173	82	243	288	37	2925
	319	6	246	79	157	171	155	163	153	160	166	164	167	169	108	217	321	4	2925
	274	51	111	214	168	154	170	162	172	165	159	161	158	156	227	98	287	38	2925
	299	26	96	223	221	66	70	110	250	231	93	76	241	256	97	245	31	294	2925
	17	308	229	102	104	259	255	215	75	94	232	249	84	69	228	80	56	269	2925
	266	307	45	57	275	29	315	20	35	277	291	323	9	292	282	44	28	30	2925
	59	18	280	268	50	296	10	305	290	48	34	2	316	33	43	281	297	295	2925
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

65	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925	
	1	3	323	321	320	6	318	8	9	315	11	313	312	14	310	16	17	308	2925
	324	322	2	4	5	319	7	317	316	10	314	12	13	311	15	309	19	306	2925
	49	276	127	198	131	121	202	196	79	246	255	73	245	247	83	72	307	18	2925
	275	50	185	140	194	204	123	129	259	66	70	252	80	78	242	253	305	20	2925
	51	274	176	149	153	172	133	192	68	257	104	223	222	101	230	95	304	21	2925
	273	52	152	173	171	154	141	184	81	244	221	102	103	224	99	226	22	303	2925
	272	53	137	188	167	158	135	190	94	231	105	219	218	108	67	258	302	23	2925
	54	271	134	191	162	163	200	125	229	96	220	106	107	217	91	234	24	301	2925
	270	55	132	193	159	166	144	181	240	85	109	215	214	112	88	237	25	300	2925
	56	269	179	146	168	157	203	122	256	69	216	110	111	213	250	75	299	26	2925
	57	268	201	124	161	164	177	148	93	232	113	210	211	116	254	71	27	298	2925
	267	58	195	130	155	170	138	187	251	74	212	115	114	209	225	100	297	28	2925
	59	266	150	175	169	156	183	142	65	260	117	206	207	120	238	87	296	29	2925
	265	60	182	143	160	165	136	189	235	90	208	119	118	205	77	248	30	295	2925
	264	61	147	197	126	180	174	151	98	86	241	233	89	228	249	76	294	31	2925
	262	63	178	128	199	145	186	139	227	239	84	92	236	97	82	243	32	293	2925
	64	261	33	291	35	289	288	38	286	40	41	283	43	281	280	278	48	46	2925
	62	263	292	34	290	36	37	287	39	285	284	42	282	44	45	47	277	279	2925
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

154	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925	
	1	3	323	321	320	6	318	8	9	315	11	313	312	14	310	16	17	308	2925
	324	322	2	4	5	319	7	317	316	10	314	12	13	311	15	309	19	306	2925
	49	276	108	101	223	221	220	218	106	103	69	256	251	73	250	76	307	18	2925
	275	50	217	224	102	104	105	107	219	222	255	70	74	252	75	249	305	20	2925
	51	274	117	208	125	199	198	128	121	204	254	71	65	259	258	68	304	21	2925
	273	52	120	205	200	126	127	197	124	201	72	253	260	66	67	257	22	303	2925
	272	53	207	118	129	195	194	132	203	122	157	167	159	165	164	163	302	23	2925
	54	271	206	119	196	130	131	193	202	123	168	158	166	160	161	162	24	301	2925
	270	55	109	116	111	212	213	114	215	210	133	192	141	183	182	144	25	300	2925
	56	269	216	209	214	113	112	211	110	115	191	134	184	142	143	181	299	26	2925
	57	268	77	247	79	245	242	84	244	82	138	187	149	175	174	152	27	298	2925
	267	58	248	78	246	80	83	241	81	243	188	137	176	150	151	173	297	28	2925
	59	266	234	235	89	92	93	232	85	240	189	136	178	147	156	169	296	29	2925
	265	60	91	90	236	233	231	94	239	86	135	190	145	180	171	154	30	295	2925
	264	61	97	227	226	100	230	95	238	87	186	139	148	177	170	155	294	31	2925
	262	63	228	98	99	225	96	229	88	237	140	185	179	146	153	172	32	293	2925
	64	261	33	291	35	289	288	38	286	40	41	283	43	281	280	278	48	46	2925
	62	263	292	34	290	36	37	287	39	285	284	42	282	44	45	47	277	279	2925
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

There are total 289 **striped magic squares** in this part.

2.2 Part 2: Embedded with Symmetric Magic Rectangles

This part also contains **embedded striped magic squares** of order 6 and 10. The external part is different from the previous part. It contained symmetrical magic rectangles. See below two examples. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author's site [96].

293	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA															2925		
	303	15	322	7	311	304	10	321	27	5	309	16	51	274	44	61	276	269	2925
	22	310	3	318	14	21	315	4	298	320	6	319	267	58	281	264	49	56	2925
	8	317	29	294	290	291	32	295	36	33	316	9	286	39	65	260	265	60	2925
	25	300	296	31	35	34	293	30	289	292	19	306	43	282	255	70	272	53	2925
	312	13	301	308	2	12	26	324	18	23	297	314	275	50	254	71	38	287	2925
	305	20	24	17	323	313	299	1	307	302	28	11	268	57	258	67	48	277	2925
	123	202	116	133	204	197	155	172	154	169	147	178	46	279	68	257	62	263	2925
	195	130	209	192	121	128	170	153	171	156	180	145	285	40	259	66	288	37	2925
	214	111	137	188	193	132	150	173	176	151	146	179	63	262	72	253	54	271	2925
	115	210	183	142	200	125	175	152	149	174	177	148	41	284	69	256	59	266	2925
	203	122	182	143	110	215	165	157	164	163	159	167	273	42	280	55	261	64	2925
	196	129	186	139	120	205	160	168	161	162	166	158	52	283	45	270	278	47	2925
	118	207	144	181	216	109	87	231	250	79	239	232	82	249	99	77	237	88	2925
	213	112	187	138	126	199	238	94	75	246	86	93	243	76	226	248	78	247	2925
	135	190	140	185	134	191	80	245	101	219	218	222	104	223	108	105	244	81	2925
	113	212	141	184	131	194	97	228	224	106	107	103	221	102	217	220	91	234	2925
	201	114	208	127	189	136	240	85	229	236	242	84	98	252	90	95	225	74	2925
	124	211	117	198	206	119	233	92	96	89	83	241	227	73	235	230	100	251	2925
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

309	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925
323	1	3	321	320	319	7	8	9	315	11	313	25	300	41	284	295	30	2925
2	324	322	4	5	6	318	317	316	10	314	12	299	26	283	42	37	288	2925
13	311	15	309	308	307	19	20	21	303	23	301	298	27	43	282	31	294	2925
312	14	310	16	17	18	306	305	304	22	302	24	28	297	281	44	293	32	2925
109	215	214	112	192	193	136	198	207	120	115	139	137	188	280	45	292	33	2925
216	110	111	213	133	132	189	127	118	205	210	186	123	202	279	46	291	34	2925
85	240	97	228	126	199	149	176	141	184	145	180	204	121	47	278	35	290	2925
239	86	227	98	206	119	175	150	183	142	178	147	187	138	48	277	36	289	2925
87	238	99	226	124	201	174	151	182	143	179	146	129	196	49	276	29	296	2925
237	88	225	100	116	209	152	173	144	181	148	177	195	130	275	50	287	38	2925
236	89	224	101	212	113	197	200	140	203	117	114	135	194	51	274	39	286	2925
235	90	223	102	191	134	128	125	185	122	208	211	190	131	273	52	285	40	2925
91	234	103	222	155	171	160	163	157	169	166	164	153	167	53	271	270	56	2925
92	233	104	221	170	154	165	162	168	156	159	161	172	158	272	54	55	269	2925
93	232	219	106	81	244	69	255	71	253	252	251	75	76	247	77	79	245	2925
231	94	105	220	243	82	256	70	254	72	73	74	250	249	78	248	246	80	2925
95	230	107	218	242	83	57	267	67	265	264	263	63	64	65	259	59	257	2925
229	96	217	108	84	241	268	58	258	60	61	62	262	261	260	66	266	68	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

There are total 72 **striped magic squares** in this part.

2.3 Part 3: Cornered with Striped Magic Squares of Order 14

In the first part we have seen that the **striped magic squares** of order 14 are embedded in the **striped magic squares** of order 18. This section includes **striped magic squares** of order 18, with **striped magic squares** of order 14 positioned at the corner. See below few examples. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author’s site [96].

433	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925	
120	205	129	132	195	194	121	204	65	260	77	248	239	86	52	273	56	269	2925	
113	212	196	193	130	131	128	197	259	66	80	245	238	87	303	22	265	60	2925	
211	114	137	188	141	184	123	202	256	69	247	78	85	240	58	267	36	289	2925	
209	116	187	138	183	142	200	125	254	71	246	79	88	237	19	306	27	298	2925	
208	117	186	139	182	143	201	124	67	258	81	243	242	84	284	41	32	293	2925	
206	119	140	185	144	181	126	199	257	68	244	82	83	241	278	47	25	300	2925	
118	207	133	136	191	190	203	122	70	255	73	251	250	76	15	310	61	264	2925	
115	210	192	189	134	135	198	127	72	253	252	74	75	249	304	21	261	64	2925	
89	235	91	233	232	94	230	96	158	167	148	179	145	178	40	285	283	42	2925	
236	90	234	92	93	231	95	229	166	159	177	146	180	147	13	312	288	37	2925	
101	223	222	104	105	220	97	228	162	163	174	151	156	169	319	6	321	4	2925	
224	102	103	221	219	106	227	98	161	164	149	176	171	154	274	51	287	38	2925	
109	215	214	112	218	107	226	99	168	157	152	173	153	172	299	26	31	294	2925	
216	110	111	213	108	217	100	225	160	165	175	150	170	155	17	308	302	23	2925	
324	322	271	12	314	279	62	5	301	63	7	39	16	311	272	270	49	8	2925	
1	3	54	313	11	46	263	320	24	262	318	286	309	14	53	55	276	317	2925	
266	307	45	57	275	29	315	20	35	277	291	323	9	292	282	44	28	30	2925	
59	18	280	268	50	296	10	305	290	48	34	2	316	33	43	281	297	295	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

608	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925	
116	210	211	113	112	214	215	109	234	91	100	225	137	188	58	267	25	300	2925	
209	115	114	212	213	111	110	216	235	90	227	98	187	138	303	22	288	37	2925	
105	218	219	108	117	207	206	120	92	233	226	99	139	186	52	273	36	289	2925	
220	107	106	217	208	118	119	205	89	236	97	228	183	142	319	6	27	298	2925	
129	195	194	132	128	198	199	125	230	93	231	96	184	141	284	41	32	293	2925	
196	130	131	193	197	127	126	200	95	232	94	229	185	140	278	47	302	23	2925	
124	202	203	121	192	134	189	135	81	243	242	84	143	182	15	310	61	264	2925	
201	123	122	204	133	191	136	190	244	82	83	241	144	181	304	21	261	64	2925	
223	102	72	253	65	259	258	68	246	79	85	240	145	180	40	285	283	42	2925	
222	103	69	256	260	66	67	257	247	78	88	237	179	146	19	306	265	60	2925	
104	221	254	71	73	251	250	76	77	248	239	86	147	178	13	312	321	4	2925	
101	224	255	70	252	74	75	249	80	245	238	87	177	148	274	51	287	38	2925	
149	175	164	173	153	171	170	156	168	151	163	165	158	159	299	26	31	294	2925	
176	150	161	152	172	154	155	169	157	174	162	160	167	166	17	308	56	269	2925	
324	322	271	12	314	279	62	5	301	63	7	39	16	311	272	270	49	8	2925	
1	3	54	313	11	46	263	320	24	262	318	286	309	14	53	55	276	317	2925	
266	307	45	57	275	29	315	20	35	277	291	323	9	292	282	44	28	30	2925	
59	18	280	268	50	296	10	305	290	48	34	2	316	33	43	281	297	295	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

There are total 261 **striped squares** in this part. Out of them 100 are magic squares and

161 are semi-magic squares. Later on these semi-magic squares shall be converted in magic squares after some simplifications.

2.4 Part 4: Cornered with Striped Magic Squares of Order 12: Using Algebraic Formula $(a + b)^2 = a^2 + b^2 + 2ab$

This part is very much similar to part 3. The difference is that here we have **striped magic squares** of order 12 instead of order 14. The magic square of order 12 are already given in another work [94]. The **striped magic squares** of order 12 are cornered in such a way that we apply the formula $(a + b)^2 = a^2 + b^2 + 2ab$. Here, the $a = 12$ and $b = 6$. The expressions ab or ba are considered in different ways. See below few examples. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author’s site [96].

626	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925	
	1	323	3	321	320	6	318	8	17	308	294	31	87	238	233	80	97	240	2925
	324	2	322	4	5	319	7	317	307	18	32	293	231	94	92	245	228	85	2925
	9	315	313	11	312	14	310	16	305	20	27	298	250	75	218	107	229	96	2925
	316	10	12	314	13	311	15	309	19	306	297	28	232	93	101	224	236	89	2925
	49	276	57	268	259	66	258	67	304	21	296	29	79	246	223	102	74	251	2925
	275	50	267	58	72	253	69	256	22	303	30	295	239	86	222	103	84	241	2925
	51	274	59	266	65	260	68	257	302	23	299	26	82	243	104	221	98	227	2925
	273	52	265	60	254	71	255	70	24	301	25	300	249	76	219	106	252	73	2925
	272	53	264	61	33	291	35	289	288	38	286	40	99	226	108	217	90	235	2925
	54	271	62	263	292	34	290	36	37	287	39	285	77	248	105	220	95	230	2925
	56	269	262	63	41	283	43	281	280	46	48	278	237	78	244	91	225	100	2925
	270	55	64	261	284	42	282	44	45	279	277	47	88	247	81	234	242	83	2925
	123	213	203	115	135	196	118	214	195	113	201	124	165	157	164	163	159	167	2925
	202	112	122	210	190	129	207	111	130	212	114	211	160	168	161	162	166	158	2925
	116	209	137	183	182	186	140	187	144	141	208	117	147	178	150	173	176	151	2925
	133	192	188	142	143	139	185	138	181	184	127	198	180	145	175	152	149	174	2925
	204	121	193	200	110	120	134	216	126	131	189	206	146	179	155	172	169	154	2925
	197	128	132	125	215	205	191	109	199	194	136	119	177	148	170	153	156	171	2925
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

908	semi	18x18	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																3595
29	296	21	304	1	324	37	288	274	52	275	49	73	252	85	240	93	232	2925	
295	30	303	22	323	2	43	282	51	273	50	276	251	74	239	86	231	94	2925	
31	294	23	302	319	6	39	286	56	270	53	271	75	250	87	238	95	230	2925	
293	32	301	24	321	4	285	40	269	55	272	54	249	76	237	88	229	96	2925	
292	33	300	25	320	5	284	41	264	61	65	260	248	77	236	89	228	97	2925	
34	291	26	299	11	314	283	42	267	58	259	66	247	78	90	235	98	227	2925	
290	35	298	27	7	318	287	38	59	266	67	258	79	246	234	91	226	99	2925	
36	289	28	297	8	317	44	281	265	60	72	253	80	245	92	233	100	225	2925	
17	307	306	20	9	316	45	280	57	268	256	69	81	244	101	223	222	104	2925	
308	18	19	305	315	10	279	46	62	263	70	255	243	82	224	102	103	221	2925	
13	311	310	16	3	322	47	278	262	63	254	71	83	242	105	219	218	108	2925	
312	14	15	309	313	12	277	48	64	261	257	68	241	84	220	106	107	217	2925	
109	215	111	213	212	211	115	116	117	207	119	205	165	157	164	163	159	167	2925	
216	110	214	112	113	114	210	209	208	118	206	120	160	168	161	162	166	158	2925	
121	203	123	201	200	126	198	128	137	188	141	184	147	178	150	173	176	151	2925	
204	122	202	124	125	199	127	197	187	138	183	142	180	145	175	152	149	174	2925	
129	195	131	193	192	134	190	136	186	139	182	143	146	179	155	172	169	154	2925	
196	130	194	132	133	191	135	189	140	185	144	181	177	148	170	153	156	171	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

954	semi	18x18	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2971
17	308	27	320	299	4	53	272	63	284	263	40	73	252	85	239	238	88	2925	
20	305	298	5	26	321	286	39	262	41	62	285	251	74	240	86	87	237	2925	
303	22	34	291	12	313	267	58	65	260	48	277	75	250	89	235	234	92	2925	
8	317	292	33	7	318	44	281	256	69	43	282	249	76	236	90	91	233	2925	
322	3	35	290	311	14	56	269	70	255	271	54	248	77	93	231	230	96	2925	
13	312	294	31	21	304	49	276	258	67	57	268	247	78	232	94	95	229	2925	
302	23	32	293	19	306	52	273	68	257	55	270	79	246	97	227	226	100	2925	
314	11	295	30	300	25	278	47	259	66	275	50	80	245	228	98	99	225	2925	
310	15	289	36	9	316	274	51	253	72	45	280	81	244	101	223	222	104	2925	
16	309	29	296	324	1	266	59	71	254	288	37	243	82	224	102	103	221	2925	
301	319	28	2	315	10	265	283	64	38	279	46	83	242	105	219	218	108	2925	
24	6	297	323	307	18	60	42	261	287	264	61	241	84	220	106	107	217	2925	
109	215	111	213	212	211	115	116	117	207	119	205	159	167	164	163	165	157	2925	
216	110	214	112	113	114	210	209	208	118	206	120	166	158	161	162	160	168	2925	
121	204	125	200	129	196	133	192	137	188	141	184	155	170	150	175	147	178	2925	
203	122	199	126	195	130	191	134	187	138	183	142	172	153	173	152	180	145	2925	
202	123	198	127	194	131	190	135	186	139	182	143	154	171	176	149	177	148	2925	
124	201	128	197	132	193	136	189	140	185	144	181	169	156	151	174	146	179	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

There are total 539 striped squares in this part. Out of them 259 are magic squares and

280 are semi-magic squares. Later on these semi-magic squares shall be converted in magic squares after some simplifications.

2.5 Part 5: Cornered with Striped Magic Squares of Order 12

This part is very much similar to part 4. The difference is that here we haven't divided the magic squares and/or magic rectangles in terms of the algebraic expressions $(a + b)^2 = a^2 + b^2 + 2ab$. The lower part we have just considered as **striped magic rectangles** of order 6×18 . This we have taken in different forms. The upper part is with **striped magic squares** of order 12 and **striped magic rectangles** of order 6×12 or better 12×6 (vertical order). See below few examples. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author's site [96].

1163	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925		
		41	302	289	278	42	24	21	303	38	287	312	13	87	238	233	240	80	97	2925
		284	23	36	47	283	301	304	22	25	300	18	307	231	94	92	85	245	228	2925
		277	48	52	273	53	272	57	268	294	31	10	315	250	75	101	224	229	96	2925
		29	296	275	50	271	54	267	58	46	279	308	17	79	246	219	106	236	89	2925
		28	297	274	51	270	55	266	59	292	33	306	19	239	86	218	107	74	251	2925
		298	27	49	276	56	269	60	265	280	45	15	310	232	93	222	103	84	241	2925
		44	281	291	286	43	293	285	30	35	37	319	6	82	243	104	221	98	227	2925
		299	26	34	39	282	32	40	295	290	288	8	317	249	76	223	102	252	73	2925
		313	320	1	322	2	4	316	311	20	16	11	314	99	226	108	217	90	235	2925
		12	5	324	3	323	321	9	14	305	309	318	7	77	248	105	220	95	230	2925
		259	262	254	64	65	68	69	263	258	255	72	61	237	78	244	91	225	100	2925
		66	63	71	261	260	257	256	62	67	70	253	264	88	247	81	234	242	83	2925
		112	205	181	128	133	111	115	209	140	200	123	211	203	191	207	131	188	137	2925
		213	120	144	197	192	214	210	116	185	125	202	114	122	134	118	194	117	208	2925
		138	187	151	175	169	155	164	153	152	166	157	176	171	163	158	165	216	109	2925
		113	212	174	150	156	170	161	172	173	159	168	149	154	162	167	160	129	196	2925
		204	121	193	189	199	186	190	127	180	142	201	119	147	110	148	182	141	146	2925
		195	130	132	136	126	139	135	198	145	183	124	206	178	215	177	143	184	179	2925
		2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

1564	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925		
	52	274	275	49	48	277	53	272	295	294	29	32	73	252	238	88	239	85	2925	
	273	51	50	276	278	47	271	54	30	31	296	293	247	78	87	237	86	240	2925	
	282	44	283	41	279	46	270	55	318	8	5	319	75	250	92	235	234	89	2925	
	43	281	42	284	45	280	56	269	7	317	320	6	249	76	233	90	91	236	2925	
	65	260	60	265	61	263	64	262	1	323	322	4	251	74	93	231	230	96	2925	
	259	66	266	59	264	62	261	63	324	2	3	321	248	77	232	94	95	229	2925	
	258	67	267	58	255	69	254	72	314	315	12	9	79	246	97	227	226	100	2925	
	68	257	57	268	70	256	71	253	11	10	313	316	80	245	228	98	99	225	2925	
	16	309	21	304	17	308	298	27	290	35	37	288	81	244	101	223	222	104	2925	
	310	15	24	301	307	18	299	26	291	34	40	285	243	82	224	102	103	221	2925	
	13	312	303	22	306	19	28	297	33	292	287	38	83	242	105	219	218	108	2925	
	311	14	302	23	20	305	25	300	36	289	286	39	241	84	220	106	107	217	2925	
	109	215	111	213	116	114	210	212	157	168	189	191	140	188	133	138	186	135	2925	
	216	110	214	112	209	211	115	113	167	158	136	134	185	137	192	187	139	190	2925	
	119	207	117	205	204	122	202	124	159	166	141	183	143	181	180	146	178	148	2925	
	206	118	208	120	121	203	123	201	165	160	184	142	182	144	145	179	147	177	2925	
	199	132	127	125	196	130	194	197	164	161	149	175	151	173	172	154	170	156	2925	
	126	193	198	200	129	195	131	128	163	162	176	150	174	152	153	171	155	169	2925	
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

1693	semi	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2559		
	13	318	293	298	294	18	313	11	37	30	38	287	87	238	80	97	240	233	2925	
	312	7	32	27	31	307	12	314	288	295	6	319	231	94	245	228	85	92	2925	
	286	39	279	48	267	52	270	59	265	60	34	291	250	75	101	224	229	96	2925	
	317	8	46	277	58	273	55	266	49	276	306	19	79	246	219	106	236	89	2925	
	21	304	50	275	263	64	262	61	56	269	299	26	239	86	218	107	74	251	2925	
	1	324	57	268	62	261	63	264	280	45	22	303	232	93	222	103	84	241	2925	
	17	308	272	53	43	284	47	283	274	44	302	23	82	243	104	221	98	227	2925	
	322	3	271	54	282	41	278	42	51	281	2	323	249	76	223	102	252	73	2925	
	316	9	256	72	67	257	254	70	65	259	301	24	99	226	108	217	90	235	2925	
	305	20	69	253	258	68	71	255	260	66	315	10	77	248	105	220	95	230	2925	
	4	321	296	40	300	14	290	28	33	309	310	5	237	78	244	91	225	100	2925	
	36	289	29	285	25	311	35	297	292	16	15	320	88	247	81	234	242	83	2925	
	109	215	111	213	212	114	210	116	157	168	189	191	140	133	188	138	186	135	2925	
	216	110	214	112	113	211	115	209	167	158	136	134	185	192	137	187	139	190	2925	
	125	199	198	128	121	204	117	208	159	166	141	184	145	180	152	174	175	149	2925	
	200	126	127	197	203	122	207	118	165	160	183	142	179	146	173	151	150	176	2925	
	129	195	194	132	202	123	206	119	164	161	182	143	178	147	153	170	171	156	2925	
	196	130	131	193	124	201	120	205	163	162	144	181	148	177	172	155	154	169	2925	
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

There are total 798 striped squares in this part. Out of them 406 are magic squares and

392 are semi-magic squares. Later on these semi-magic squares shall be converted in magic squares after some simplifications.

2.6 Part 6: Cornered with Striped Magic Squares of Order 10 Using Algebraic Formula $(a + b)^2 = a^2 + b^2 + 2ab$

This part is very much similar to Parts 3 and 4. The difference is that here we have **striped magic squares** of order 10 instead of orders 12 and 14. The **striped magic squares** of order 10 are already given in another work [94]. The **striped magic squares** of order 10 are cornered in such a way that we apply the formula $(a + b)^2 = a^2 + b^2 + 2ab$. Here, we have taken $a = 10$ and $b = 8$. The expressions ab or ba are considered in different ways. See below few examples. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author's site [96].

1961	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925	
	115	113	211	209	208	118	206	120	121	204	308	17	13	18	297	309	19	319	2925
	210	212	114	116	117	207	119	205	123	202	7	318	312	307	28	16	306	6	2925
	137	188	155	170	150	175	147	178	203	122	299	26	29	294	295	32	1	324	2925
	187	138	172	153	173	152	180	145	201	124	313	12	296	31	30	293	298	27	2925
	139	186	154	171	176	149	146	179	200	125	323	2	291	33	290	36	321	4	2925
	185	140	169	156	151	174	177	148	126	199	22	303	34	292	35	289	315	10	2925
	184	141	165	157	164	163	159	167	198	127	8	317	37	287	286	40	24	301	2925
	182	143	160	168	161	162	166	158	128	197	20	305	288	38	39	285	311	14	2925
	144	181	129	195	131	193	136	134	190	192	25	5	310	322	11	302	21	304	2925
	142	183	196	130	194	132	189	191	135	133	300	320	15	3	314	23	9	316	2925
	268	48	259	273	283	62	47	60	65	260	92	234	235	89	88	237	93	232	2925
	57	277	66	52	42	263	278	265	45	280	233	91	90	236	238	87	231	94	2925
	53	272	69	256	73	252	77	248	270	55	81	243	242	84	239	86	230	95	2925
	58	267	255	70	251	74	247	78	282	43	244	82	83	241	85	240	96	229	2925
	279	46	254	71	250	75	246	79	51	274	105	220	100	225	104	222	223	101	2925
	269	56	72	253	76	249	80	245	262	63	219	106	226	99	221	103	102	224	2925
	59	266	41	258	281	275	64	271	61	49	218	107	227	98	109	215	214	112	2925
	257	68	284	67	44	50	261	54	264	276	108	217	97	228	216	110	111	213	2925
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

2831	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925		
		153	170	171	156	133	192	205	120	125	200	40	286	287	37	290	33	291	36	2925
		172	155	154	169	191	134	204	121	199	126	285	39	38	288	35	292	34	289	2925
		145	179	148	178	135	190	119	206	127	198	312	305	24	297	26	11	15	310	2925
		180	146	177	147	188	137	124	201	197	128	13	20	301	28	299	314	302	23	2925
		149	175	174	152	189	136	202	123	196	129	308	17	30	293	31	296	315	10	2925
		176	150	151	173	138	187	122	203	130	195	22	303	295	32	294	29	18	307	2925
		141	183	182	144	186	139	207	118	194	131	311	14	19	313	298	16	25	304	2925
		184	142	143	181	140	185	117	208	132	193	9	316	306	12	27	309	300	21	2925
		157	167	159	165	164	163	113	211	116	210	1	323	3	321	320	6	318	8	2925
		168	158	166	160	161	162	212	114	209	115	324	2	322	4	5	319	7	317	2925
		41	284	272	53	271	49	62	268	73	252	92	234	235	89	88	238	239	85	2925
		280	45	257	68	54	276	263	57	251	74	233	91	90	236	237	87	86	240	2925
		43	282	64	261	256	69	59	266	250	75	81	243	242	84	93	231	230	96	2925
		281	44	51	274	71	254	273	52	76	249	244	82	83	241	232	94	95	229	2925
		48	277	66	259	253	72	258	67	77	248	105	219	218	108	104	222	223	101	2925
		46	279	265	60	70	255	56	269	247	78	220	106	107	217	221	103	102	224	2925
		283	42	55	262	275	58	65	260	246	79	100	226	227	97	109	215	214	112	2925
		278	47	270	63	50	267	264	61	80	245	225	99	98	228	216	110	111	213	2925
		2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

3286	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925		
		141	184	133	192	162	163	145	180	153	172	9	316	304	21	303	30	17	300	2925
		183	142	190	135	161	164	148	177	156	169	315	10	289	36	22	295	308	25	2925
		182	143	191	134	166	159	178	147	170	155	11	314	32	293	288	37	27	298	2925
		144	181	136	189	160	165	179	146	171	154	313	12	34	291	39	286	305	20	2925
		137	187	186	140	158	167	149	175	174	152	312	13	19	306	285	40	290	35	2925
		188	138	139	185	168	157	176	150	151	173	14	311	297	28	38	287	24	301	2925
		113	212	124	205	119	207	202	204	117	122	310	15	23	294	307	26	33	292	2925
		210	115	201	120	206	118	123	121	208	203	16	309	302	31	18	299	296	29	2925
		211	114	125	199	127	194	132	130	196	197	1	323	3	321	320	6	318	8	2925
		116	209	200	126	198	131	193	195	129	128	324	2	322	4	5	319	7	317	2925
		49	275	51	273	272	270	54	56	41	284	92	237	236	84	82	244	226	99	2925
		276	50	274	52	53	55	271	269	283	42	233	88	89	241	243	81	239	86	2925
		264	249	74	59	72	257	63	262	43	282	94	231	219	105	218	108	227	98	2925
		61	76	251	266	253	68	254	71	281	44	230	95	106	220	107	217	85	240	2925
		263	62	248	245	79	78	267	58	280	45	228	97	214	112	109	215	96	229	2925
		70	255	77	80	246	247	66	259	46	279	242	83	111	213	216	110	102	223	2925
		260	65	67	265	250	64	73	256	278	47	91	234	225	232	104	103	224	87	2925
		57	268	258	60	75	261	252	69	48	277	90	235	100	93	221	222	101	238	2925
		2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

There are total 1600 striped squares in this part. Out of them 1440 are magic squares and

160 are semi-magic squares. Later on these semi-magic squares shall be converted in magic squares after some simplifications.

2.7 Part 7: Embedded with Striped Magic Squares of Order 14

This part is very much similar to part 5. The difference is that here we haven't divided the magic squares and/or magic rectangles in terms of the algebraic expressions $(a + b)^2 = a^2 + b^2 + 2ab$. The lower part we have just considered as magic rectangles of order 8×18 . This we have taken different forms. The upper part is with striped magic squares of order 10 and magic rectangles of order 8×10 or better 10×8 (vertical order). See below few examples. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author's site [96].

3561	semi	18x18	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2831
	115	113	211	209	208	118	206	120	121	204	73	251	75	249	248	78	246	80	2925
	210	212	114	116	117	207	119	205	123	202	252	74	250	76	77	247	79	245	2925
	137	188	155	172	154	169	147	178	203	122	81	243	83	241	240	86	238	88	2925
	187	138	170	153	171	156	180	145	201	124	244	82	242	84	85	239	87	237	2925
	139	186	150	173	176	151	146	179	200	125	89	235	91	233	232	94	230	96	2925
	185	140	175	152	149	174	177	148	126	199	236	90	234	92	93	231	95	229	2925
	184	141	165	157	164	163	159	167	198	127	97	227	99	225	224	102	222	104	2925
	182	143	160	168	161	162	166	158	128	197	228	98	226	100	101	223	103	221	2925
	144	181	129	195	131	193	136	134	190	192	105	219	107	217	216	110	214	112	2925
	142	183	196	130	194	132	189	191	135	133	220	106	218	108	109	215	111	213	2925
	1	324	9	316	17	308	25	300	33	292	283	42	49	276	264	61	70	255	2925
	323	2	315	10	307	18	299	26	291	34	281	44	275	50	62	263	259	66	2925
	3	322	11	314	19	306	27	298	35	290	43	282	56	269	59	266	65	260	2925
	321	4	313	12	305	20	297	28	289	36	41	284	273	52	265	60	257	68	2925
	320	5	312	13	304	21	296	29	288	37	280	45	272	53	267	58	256	69	2925
	6	319	14	311	22	303	30	295	38	287	46	279	54	271	57	268	254	71	2925
	318	7	310	15	302	23	294	31	286	39	278	47	270	55	262	63	72	253	2925
	8	317	16	309	24	301	32	293	40	285	48	277	51	274	64	261	67	258	2925
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

3583	semi	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2670		
		115	113	211	209	208	118	206	120	121	204	81	244	89	236	105	220	109	216	2925
		210	212	114	116	117	207	119	205	123	202	243	82	235	90	219	106	215	110	2925
		137	188	155	170	150	175	147	178	203	122	83	242	91	234	218	107	214	111	2925
		187	138	172	153	173	152	180	145	201	124	241	84	233	92	108	217	112	213	2925
		139	186	154	171	176	149	146	179	200	125	240	85	232	93	101	223	222	104	2925
		185	140	169	156	151	174	177	148	126	199	86	239	94	231	224	102	103	221	2925
		184	141	165	157	164	163	159	167	198	127	238	87	230	95	97	227	226	100	2925
		182	143	160	168	161	162	166	158	128	197	88	237	96	229	228	98	99	225	2925
		144	181	129	195	131	193	136	134	190	192	73	251	75	249	248	78	246	80	2925
		142	183	196	130	194	132	189	191	135	133	252	74	250	76	77	247	79	245	2925
		65	260	1	9	3	321	320	6	318	8	323	315	11	313	312	14	310	16	2925
		259	66	324	316	322	4	5	319	7	317	2	10	314	12	13	311	15	309	2925
		67	258	17	307	19	305	304	22	302	24	25	299	27	296	297	30	294	32	2925
		257	68	308	18	306	20	21	303	23	301	300	26	298	29	28	295	31	293	2925
		256	69	46	291	35	289	288	38	286	40	41	283	43	280	281	33	278	48	2925
		70	255	279	34	290	36	37	287	39	285	284	42	282	45	44	292	47	277	2925
		254	71	64	275	51	273	272	54	270	56	57	267	59	265	264	262	62	49	2925
		72	253	261	50	274	52	53	271	55	269	268	58	266	60	61	63	263	276	2925
		2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

3630	semi	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																3084		
		149	175	174	152	145	180	187	138	198	127	236	89	85	90	247	237	91	225	2925
		176	150	151	173	179	146	137	188	128	197	80	245	240	235	78	88	234	100	2925
		144	182	141	183	178	147	186	139	123	202	227	98	101	223	222	104	73	252	2925
		181	143	184	142	148	177	140	185	201	124	241	84	224	102	103	221	226	99	2925
		129	134	131	193	190	192	195	136	200	125	251	74	105	219	218	108	249	76	2925
		196	191	194	132	135	133	130	189	126	199	94	231	220	106	107	217	243	82	2925
		115	209	113	211	208	118	206	120	121	204	79	246	109	215	214	112	96	229	2925
		210	116	212	114	117	207	119	205	203	122	92	233	216	110	111	213	239	86	2925
		155	171	160	163	157	167	166	164	153	169	97	77	238	250	83	230	93	232	2925
		170	154	165	162	168	158	159	161	172	156	228	248	87	75	242	95	81	244	2925
		65	260	1	323	3	321	320	6	318	8	315	9	11	313	312	14	310	16	2925
		259	66	324	2	322	4	5	319	7	317	10	316	314	12	13	311	15	309	2925
		67	258	17	307	19	305	304	22	302	24	25	299	27	297	296	30	294	32	2925
		257	68	308	18	306	20	21	303	23	301	300	26	298	28	29	295	31	293	2925
		256	69	57	268	61	264	33	283	35	289	288	287	39	40	41	291	43	281	2925
		70	255	267	58	263	62	292	42	290	36	37	38	286	285	284	34	282	44	2925
		254	71	266	59	262	63	45	279	47	277	276	275	51	52	53	271	269	55	2925
		72	253	60	265	64	261	280	46	278	48	49	50	274	273	272	54	56	270	2925
		2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

There are total 480 striped squares in this part. All of them are semi-magic squares. Later

all of on these semi-magic squares shall be converted in magic squares after some simplifications.

2.8 Part 8: Some Extra Magic Squares of Order 18

This part is not following any specific rule. These are just constructed based on some general idea. Any how all of them looks beautiful. See below few examples. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author’s site [96].

4041	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925	
	1	324	21	304	298	28	25	299	33	292	53	272	266	60	57	267	70	255	2925
	323	2	10	315	27	297	300	26	291	34	42	283	59	265	268	58	254	71	2925
	3	322	311	14	295	30	308	17	35	290	279	46	263	62	276	49	65	260	2925
	321	4	303	22	32	293	16	309	289	36	271	54	64	261	273	52	257	68	2925
	320	5	312	13	294	31	24	301	288	37	280	45	262	63	56	269	256	69	2925
	6	319	18	307	29	296	9	316	38	287	50	275	61	264	41	284	259	66	2925
	318	7	310	11	306	23	305	20	286	39	43	278	274	55	48	277	72	253	2925
	8	317	15	314	19	302	313	12	40	285	282	47	51	270	281	44	67	258	2925
	165	149	167	153	174	164	178	157	177	156	163	159	170	146	154	173	175	145	2925
	160	176	158	172	151	161	147	168	148	169	162	166	155	179	171	152	150	180	2925
	246	79	93	232	226	100	97	227	105	220	125	200	194	132	129	195	137	188	2925
	80	245	82	243	99	225	228	98	219	106	114	211	131	193	196	130	187	138	2925
	75	250	240	85	101	224	236	89	107	218	207	118	191	134	204	121	144	181	2925
	249	76	231	94	104	221	233	92	217	108	199	126	136	189	113	212	185	140	2925
	248	77	239	86	222	103	96	229	216	109	208	117	190	135	128	197	184	141	2925
	78	247	90	235	223	102	81	244	110	215	122	203	133	192	201	124	142	183	2925
	251	74	238	83	234	95	88	237	214	111	206	115	202	127	120	205	182	143	2925
	73	252	87	242	91	230	241	84	112	213	119	210	123	198	209	116	139	186	2925
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

4050	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925		
	22	304	23	301	20	305	12	313	33	292	257	68	43	282	53	272	62	263	2925	
	303	21	302	24	306	19	314	11	291	34	67	258	41	284	271	54	63	262	2925	
	13	311	310	16	307	18	315	10	35	290	72	253	280	45	270	55	264	61	2925	
	312	14	15	309	17	308	9	316	289	36	256	69	281	44	56	269	261	64	2925	
	3	318	323	321	320	1	6	8	288	37	254	71	278	47	60	266	267	57	2925	
	322	7	2	4	5	324	319	317	38	287	70	255	283	42	265	59	58	268	2925	
	297	27	32	296	294	30	25	299	286	39	65	260	46	279	52	274	275	49	2925	
	28	298	293	29	31	295	300	26	40	285	259	66	48	277	273	51	50	276	2925	
	165	149	167	153	174	164	178	157	177	154	163	159	170	146	156	173	175	145	2925	
	160	176	158	172	151	161	147	168	148	171	162	166	155	179	169	152	150	180	2925	
	84	242	243	81	75	250	225	100	105	220	185	139	144	184	182	142	137	187	2925	
	241	83	82	244	251	74	99	226	219	106	140	186	181	141	143	183	188	138	2925	
	92	234	235	89	73	252	104	221	107	218	115	113	211	209	208	206	118	120	2925	
	233	91	90	236	249	76	224	101	217	108	210	212	114	116	117	119	207	205	2925	
	95	230	239	86	248	77	222	103	216	109	124	201	132	193	125	199	198	128	2925	
	229	96	88	237	246	79	102	223	110	215	202	123	194	131	200	126	127	197	2925	
	94	231	238	87	78	247	97	228	214	111	203	122	195	130	134	192	135	189	2925	
	232	93	85	240	80	245	227	98	112	213	121	204	129	196	191	133	190	136	2925	
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

4095	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925		
	50	6	13	19	314	291	14	27	321	48	316	310	268	2	322	279	274	51	2925	
	275	319	312	306	11	34	311	298	4	277	9	15	57	323	3	46	55	270	2925	
	17	308	99	227	62	236	256	73	232	86	241	233	104	101	237	88	41	284	2925	
	283	42	226	98	263	89	69	252	93	239	84	92	221	224	103	222	265	60	2925	
	47	278	229	96	109	198	130	204	209	132	107	211	203	122	238	87	285	40	2925	
	20	305	228	97	216	127	195	121	116	193	218	114	126	199	230	95	292	33	2925	
	32	293	102	223	208	117	133	192	137	188	141	184	124	201	248	77	39	286	2925	
	318	7	264	61	108	217	191	134	187	138	183	142	194	131	82	243	22	303	2925	
	302	23	262	63	196	129	190	135	186	139	182	143	215	110	64	261	49	276	2925	
	297	28	225	100	128	197	136	189	140	185	144	181	113	212	246	79	320	5	2925	
	37	288	81	244	115	210	207	202	119	125	112	111	205	219	94	231	294	31	2925	
	290	35	65	260	220	105	118	123	206	200	213	214	120	106	83	242	10	315	2925	
	21	304	78	247	80	254	240	250	253	66	251	67	255	76	90	68	30	295	2925	
	272	53	91	234	245	71	85	75	72	259	74	258	70	249	235	257	299	26	2925	
	301	24	29	313	58	1	44	59	8	54	289	273	309	269	282	307	280	25	2925	
	38	287	296	12	267	324	281	266	317	271	36	52	16	56	43	18	45	300	2925	
	165	146	167	153	174	164	178	157	177	156	163	159	170	149	154	173	175	145	2925	
	160	179	158	172	151	161	147	168	148	169	162	166	155	176	171	152	150	180	2925	
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

There are total 58 striped squares in this part. All of them 39 are magic squares and 19

are semi-magic squares. Later all of on these semi-magic squares shall be converted in magic squares after some simplifications.

2.9 Part 9: Cornered with Striped Magic Squares of Order 16

This Part is very much similar to Part 3. He we have take striped magic squares of order 16 at the corner and then adjusted them in square of order 18. See below some examples:

4132	semi	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																3310		
		8	1	323	321	320	318	6	3	38	33	291	289	288	286	40	35	129	196	2925
		317	324	2	4	5	7	319	322	287	292	34	36	37	39	285	290	195	130	2925
		17	308	25	300	29	296	21	304	49	276	57	268	64	261	53	272	131	194	2925
		20	305	299	26	295	30	24	301	52	273	267	58	263	62	56	269	193	132	2925
		307	18	298	27	294	31	303	22	275	50	266	59	262	63	271	54	192	133	2925
		306	19	28	297	32	293	302	23	274	51	60	265	61	264	270	55	134	191	2925
		9	16	11	312	313	14	315	310	41	48	43	280	281	46	283	278	190	135	2925
		316	309	314	13	12	311	10	15	284	277	282	45	44	279	42	47	136	189	2925
		242	100	247	244	249	72	93	254	73	235	69	98	66	233	65	260	137	188	2925
		83	225	78	81	76	253	232	71	252	90	256	227	259	92	239	86	187	138	2925
		223	102	105	220	215	110	113	212	117	208	202	123	125	200	234	91	139	186	2925
		236	89	219	106	112	213	211	114	207	118	203	122	199	126	94	231	185	140	2925
		96	229	218	107	214	111	210	115	206	119	121	204	198	127	103	222	184	141	2925
		255	70	108	217	109	216	116	209	120	205	124	201	128	197	240	85	142	183	2925
		88	237	97	238	74	226	224	243	104	95	257	75	67	246	245	84	182	143	2925
		77	248	228	87	251	99	101	82	221	230	68	250	258	79	80	241	144	181	2925
		165	149	167	145	174	164	178	157	177	156	163	159	170	146	175	173	154	153	2925
		160	176	158	180	151	161	147	168	148	169	162	166	155	179	150	152	171	172	2925
		2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2994

4216	mgc	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925	
	84	241	93	96	231	230	85	240	109	216	256	69	275	274	49	52	129	196	2925
	77	248	232	229	94	95	92	233	215	110	67	258	50	51	276	273	195	130	2925
	247	78	101	224	105	220	87	238	111	214	64	261	56	53	270	271	131	194	2925
	245	80	223	102	219	106	236	89	213	112	262	63	269	272	55	54	193	132	2925
	244	81	222	103	218	107	237	88	212	113	252	73	44	282	283	41	192	133	2925
	242	83	104	221	108	217	90	235	114	211	71	254	281	43	42	284	134	191	2925
	82	243	97	100	227	226	239	86	210	115	263	62	45	279	278	48	190	135	2925
	79	246	228	225	98	99	234	91	116	209	66	259	280	46	47	277	136	189	2925
	260	264	57	266	58	60	257	255	76	72	74	251	33	291	290	36	137	188	2925
	65	61	268	59	267	265	68	70	249	253	250	75	292	34	35	289	187	138	2925
	203	128	198	117	121	120	207	124	125	199	202	206	40	286	287	37	139	186	2925
	122	197	127	208	204	205	118	201	200	126	123	119	285	39	38	288	185	140	2925
	1	322	323	4	9	314	315	12	20	306	307	17	303	28	21	298	184	141	2925
	324	3	2	321	316	11	10	313	305	19	18	308	22	297	304	27	142	183	2925
	5	319	318	8	13	311	310	16	29	295	294	32	302	24	25	299	182	143	2925
	320	6	7	317	312	14	15	309	296	30	31	293	23	301	300	26	144	181	2925
	165	149	167	145	174	164	178	157	177	156	163	159	170	146	175	173	153	154	2925
	160	176	158	180	151	161	147	168	148	169	162	166	155	179	150	152	172	171	2925
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

4276	semi	18x18 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																3551	
	1	323	3	321	320	319	7	8	9	315	11	313	25	300	37	288	129	196	2925
	324	2	322	4	5	6	318	317	316	10	314	12	299	26	287	38	195	130	2925
	13	311	309	15	308	307	19	20	21	303	23	301	297	28	39	286	131	194	2925
	312	14	16	310	17	18	306	305	304	22	302	24	27	298	285	40	193	132	2925
	73	252	85	240	108	221	220	100	98	228	210	115	296	29	284	41	192	133	2925
	251	74	239	86	217	104	105	225	227	97	223	102	295	30	283	42	134	191	2925
	75	250	87	238	110	215	203	121	202	124	211	114	31	294	43	282	190	135	2925
	249	76	237	88	214	111	122	204	123	201	101	224	32	293	44	281	136	189	2925
	248	77	236	89	212	113	198	128	125	199	112	213	33	292	45	280	137	188	2925
	247	78	235	90	226	99	127	197	200	126	118	207	291	34	279	46	187	138	2925
	79	246	91	234	107	218	209	216	120	119	208	103	35	290	47	278	139	186	2925
	80	245	92	233	106	219	116	109	205	206	117	222	289	36	277	48	185	140	2925
	81	244	231	94	49	275	51	273	272	271	55	56	267	57	59	265	184	141	2925
	243	82	93	232	276	50	274	52	53	54	270	269	58	268	266	60	142	183	2925
	83	242	95	230	61	263	63	261	260	259	67	68	69	255	71	253	182	143	2925
	241	84	229	96	264	62	262	64	65	66	258	257	256	70	254	72	144	181	2925
	165	149	167	145	174	164	178	157	177	156	163	159	170	146	175	173	154	153	2925
	160	176	158	180	151	161	147	168	148	169	162	166	155	179	150	152	172	171	2925
	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

In this section, there are a total of 266 striped squares. Among these, 57 are magic squares

and 209 are semi-magic squares. These semi-magic squares will be transformed into magic squares following certain simplification

Total there are 4363 examples of **striped** magic squares of order 18. These are available as **pdf file** at the author's site [96].

3 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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- **Block-Wise Magic Squares**
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